

Polymorphism in Antidiabetic Drugs: Analytical Characterization and its Impact on Pharmaceutical Performance

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Abstract

Polymorphism is the phenomenon in which a chemical substance can crystallize in multiple structural forms. This property is highly significant in pharmaceutical development, especially for antidiabetic drugs, as different polymorphs can display variations in solubility, dissolution behavior, stability, and bioavailability. These differences ultimately affect therapeutic efficacy and manufacturing reliability. This review outlines the analytical techniques used to identify and evaluate polymorphs of antidiabetic agents, particularly metformin and dapagliflozin. Methods such as powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (ss-NMR) are discussed in terms of their accuracy, strengths, and limitations. Reported studies show that metformin requires strict control of its solid-state form to retain optimal therapeutic activity, whereas dapagliflozin undergoes polymorphic changes that can affect its stability during processing and storage. Overall, this review emphasizes the critical role of proper polymorph detection and control in ensuring the safety, quality, and clinical performance of antidiabetic formulations, providing essential insights for researchers, formulators, and regulatory bodies.

Keywords: Polymorphism, antidiabetic agents, metformin, dapagliflozin, analytical characterization, stability, bioavailability, pharmaceutical development.

1.Introduction:

Polymorphism refers to the ability of a single chemical compound to crystallize in multiple structural arrangements, known as polymorphs. Although these forms share the same molecular formula and chemical composition, they differ in the arrangement of molecules within the crystal lattice. As a result, their physical properties such as:

- Melting point

- Solubility
- Dissolution rate
- Density
- Hardness
- Stability [1,2]

In the pharmaceutical field, polymorphism plays a crucial role because such physical differences can influence a drug's bioavailability, manufacturing process, stability, and even intellectual property protection [2,3]. The specific polymorph present can determine how fast the drug dissolves, how well it is absorbed, and how effectively it exerts its therapeutic action.

Therefore, identifying and controlling polymorphic forms is an essential part of drug development and manufacturing. Analytical techniques such as Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) are widely applied to detect and differentiate between polymorphs [1,4].

2. Types of Polymorphism :

Polymorphism can be classified into two main types: *monotropic* and *enantiotropic*. This classification depends on the stability of polymorphs under varying temperature and pressure conditions. When two polymorphs are stable within different temperature ranges one form being more stable at a lower temperature and the other at a higher temperature they are referred to as enantiomer. Conversely, if one form remains stable across all temperatures below its melting point while others are unstable, the system is monotropic [5].

3. Relevance of Polymorphism in Antidiabetic Drugs :

In diabetes management, maintaining consistent and predictable drug release is vital for stable blood glucose control. Many antidiabetic medications, such as dapagliflozin (an SGLT-2 inhibitor) and metformin hydrochloride (a biguanide), are formulated as solid oral dosage forms whose effectiveness depends on their polymorphic behavior [6,7].

Dapagliflozin exists in multiple crystalline forms, including anhydrous and hydrated polymorphs, which differ in solubility and stability, influencing its therapeutic action [6]. Metformin hydrochloride, though highly soluble, also exhibits polymorphism that can affect its compressibility, flow properties, and formulation compatibility [7].

Understanding and evaluating these polymorphic forms are key to selecting the most stable and bioavailable version for formulation development. It also helps prevent unwanted transitions during production and storage, thereby maintaining product quality throughout its shelf life [4].

3.1 Metformin Hydrochloride:

Two polymorphic forms of metformin hydrochloride Form A and Form B have been reported. Form A is thermodynamically stable, whereas Form B is metastable and difficult to handle due to its instability [9]. Scott L. Childs and colleagues investigated these two forms and their mixtures using capillary crystallization and thermal microscopy, and both were found to be monoclinic (P21/c), each containing one metformin cation and one chloride anion in the asymmetric unit [10].

Figure no. 1. Metformin hydrochloride Form A and B shown, respectively at 50% probability ellipsoids [9]

3.2 Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate:

Polymorphism greatly influences the physicochemical characteristics, bioavailability, and therapeutic performance of antidiabetic drugs [1]. Dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate, a member of the SGLT-2 inhibitor class, shows several polymorphic

variations that can arise during manufacturing [11]. Understanding its polymorphic transitions is therefore essential to develop stable tablet formulations.

This compound regulates blood glucose levels by inhibiting renal glucose reabsorption, and its crystalline form can affect its solubility, compressibility, and efficacy [6,7]. Ensuring the polymorphic stability of dapagliflozin throughout formulation and compression is critical for maintaining consistent drug quality and performance [9].

In one study, experimental and computational techniques were used to evaluate the behavior of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate under compression forces similar to those used in tablet manufacturing. Model tablets prepared with excipients such as microcrystalline cellulose, lactose, and disintegrants were analyzed using X-ray diffraction with Rietveld refinement, nanoindentation, and quantum chemical simulations [18]. Results confirmed that the drug retained its original crystal structure without phase transformation or impurity formation, consistent with the reference data from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC) [11]. This integrated approach demonstrates a reliable way to predict and prevent polymorphic transitions, ensuring the drug's structural and therapeutic stability [1,17].

4. Techniques for the Characterization of Polymorphs :

Newly discovered polymorphs can be analyzed using a variety of advanced analytical techniques to confirm their identity and characteristics. Once isolated, each polymorphic form must be thoroughly examined to understand its unique structural and physical features. The most commonly employed analytical tools include crystallography, microscopy, thermal analysis, solubility testing, vibrational spectroscopy, and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). Among these, X-ray diffraction (XRD) remains the primary method for detecting polymorphic variations in pharmaceutical compounds, while other methods serve as complementary approaches. Techniques such as Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) are particularly valuable for verifying results. However, Powder X-ray Diffraction (PXRD) provides the clearest structural identification of a polymorph, much like how NMR provides detailed insights into a compound's molecular features. Each polymorphic form displays a distinct PXRD pattern that serves as its structural "fingerprint."

4.1 PXRD Analysis:

Powder X-ray Diffraction is a highly reliable method for determining the crystal structure of polymorphic materials. It helps identify differences in formation, purity, and the degree

of crystallinity [15]. PXRD patterns display variations in peak intensity, position, and number, each serving as evidence of distinct crystalline phases [21]. These variations confirm the presence or formation of new polymorphic forms.

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) is one of the most powerful and commonly employed analytical tools for the identification and characterization of polymorphs in pharmaceutical compounds. Each crystalline form produces a distinct diffraction pattern, serving as a unique fingerprint that enables precise differentiation between polymorphic structures of anti-diabetic drugs. A standard PXRD setup includes an X-ray source, two goniometers, a sample holder, a detector, and a computer interface. The X-rays are typically generated using copper (1.54 Å) or molybdenum (0.71 Å) targets and then filtered through nickel or zirconium filters to obtain a monochromatic beam before interacting with the sample. About 80–100 mg of finely powdered, randomly oriented material is used to ensure all crystallographic planes are exposed for analysis. The resulting PXRD pattern, which plots intensity versus scattering angle (2θ), reveals characteristic peaks corresponding to each crystalline form. As per the United States Pharmacopeia, two polymorphs are considered identical when the 10 strongest reflections match within $\pm 0.2^\circ$ (2θ) and their relative intensities differ by no more than 20%, though this criterion excludes solvates and hydrates [26]. PXRD can also quantify the crystallinity percentage by comparing the integrated intensities of crystalline and amorphous references. Generally, crystalline materials display sharp, well-defined peaks, whereas amorphous substances exhibit broad or no peaks [27].

4.2 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):

DSC is one of the most frequently used methods in the pharmaceutical industry for analyzing phase transitions associated with polymorphic changes. First described by Haines and Wilburn [11], this technique measures the difference in heat flow between a sample and a reference as both are heated at a controlled rate [13,14]. The resulting thermogram plots heat flow versus temperature, revealing thermal events such as melting, crystallization, or decomposition. The area under each curve corresponds to the amount of heat absorbed or released during the transition, and integrating these peaks provides the enthalpy change (heat of reaction).

Figure no. 2. Illustration of different thermal events in a typical DSC curve

4.3 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR):

FTIR spectroscopy is widely used to investigate molecular vibrations, lattice arrangements, and intermolecular interactions within polymorphs. Although polymorphs share the same chemical composition, variations in crystal packing and hydrogen bonding lead to noticeable shifts in characteristic absorption bands such as N–H, O–H, and C=O stretching vibrations [25]. These spectral patterns act as molecular “signatures” distinguishing one polymorph from another. For example, FTIR analysis has successfully differentiated various polymorphs and hydrates of metformin hydrochloride based on shifts in band positions linked to different hydrogen-bonding networks [17]. The technique is non-destructive, rapid, and highly effective in distinguishing crystalline forms. Studies have shown that combining FTIR with PXRD and thermal analysis enhances the accuracy of polymorph identification and ensures better control over drug quality and stability [18].

Studies on several polymorphic systems such as tegafur [28], etoposide [29], and carbamazepine [30] revealed only minor spectral differences, implying limited influence of crystal structure on molecular vibration patterns. In contrast, ranitidine hydrochloride

[31] and mexiletine hydrochloride [32] demonstrated significant frequency shifts, indicating that variations in lattice arrangement can markedly affect molecular vibrations. FT-IR spectroscopy also plays an essential role in differentiating solvated and anhydrous phases. Incorporation of solvent molecules into the lattice modifies the vibrational frequencies, particularly in the 3600–3100 cm^{-1} region associated with O–H and N–H stretching [33–35]. Hydrated forms such as digoxin [33], ampicillin [34], and trazodone hydrochloride [35] exhibit distinct spectral changes compared to their anhydrous counterparts.

4.4 Solid-State Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (ssNMR) :

Solid-state NMR is a powerful analytical tool for examining crystalline pharmaceuticals, particularly when compounds are insoluble or poorly soluble. Unlike solution NMR, ssNMR allows for direct analysis of solid samples, offering detailed information about atomic-level environments. It is highly sensitive to molecular packing, hydrogen bonding, and conformational variations within the crystal lattice [1]. Each polymorph exhibits distinct chemical shifts and relaxation behaviors, reflecting its unique crystal structure. For example, ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR has been used to distinguish between polymorphic and hydrated forms of metformin hydrochloride, supporting findings from FTIR and PXRD studies [17,19]. ssNMR is non-destructive, reproducible, and provides essential structural information crucial for regulatory documentation and ensuring batch-to-batch uniformity [19,20].

Figure no. 3 : Typical NMR spectra of polymorph**5. Impact of Polymorphism on Drug Performance :**

Polymorphism has a profound impact on the physicochemical and biopharmaceutical behavior of drugs, influencing their therapeutic performance and manufacturing consistency:

- **Dissolution rate:** Stable polymorphs typically dissolve more slowly than metastable forms due to their lower free energy, affecting drug absorption rates [23].
- **Absorption and bioavailability:** Variations in solubility among polymorphs can cause differences in plasma concentration and bioavailability [22].
- **Therapeutic effectiveness:** Low-solubility or poorly bioavailable polymorphs may lead to reduced clinical efficacy [16].
- **Manufacturing performance:** Phase transitions during production can alter tablet hardness, friability, and disintegration behavior, resulting in inconsistency in product quality [24].

Therefore, maintaining a uniform and stable polymorphic form throughout formulation and manufacturing is essential for ensuring consistent therapeutic outcomes, product reliability, and regulatory compliance [11].

6. Conclusion:

Polymorphism plays a vital role in determining the solubility, stability, and bioavailability of antidiabetic drugs, which directly affects both therapeutic performance and formulation success. A well-integrated approach involving the identification and characterization of polymorphic forms is critical for ensuring consistent drug quality and efficacy. The combination of experimental techniques with computational modeling enhances the understanding and prediction of polymorphic behavior, enabling the development of stable and high-performing formulations. Ultimately, effective control and monitoring of polymorphism are essential for producing safe, reliable, and high-quality pharmaceutical products.

REFERENCES

1. Brittain HG, editor. *Polymorphism in Pharmaceutical Solids*. 2nd ed. New York: Informa Healthcare; 2009.
2. Bernstein J. *Polymorphism in Molecular Crystals*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2002.
3. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Guidance for Industry. ANDAs: Pharmaceutical Solid Polymorphism – Chemistry, Manufacturing, and Controls Information. 2007.
4. Shi Q, Chen H, Wang Y, Xu J, Liu Z. Recent advances in drug polymorphs: aspects of pharmaceutical properties and selective crystallization. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.*2021;172:50–67.
5. Purohit R, Paloth V. Polymorphism: an overview. *Resonance*. 2009 Sep;14(9):882–893. doi:10.1007/s12045-009-0084-7.
6. Chon J, Jones G. Crystallographic study of dapagliflozin polymorphs. *J Med Chem*. 2013;56(5):1741–1750.
7. Li Q. Solid-state characterization of metformin hydrochloride polymorphs. *Int J Pharm*. 2009;379(1):121–128.
8. Chadha R, Rani D, Goyal P. Role of crystallization in genesis of diverse crystal forms of antidiabetic agents. In: *Advances in Crystallization Processes* [Internet]. IntechOpen; 2012 [cited 2025 Oct 7]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/59674>
9. Scott LC, Leonard JC, Jeanette TD, David AC, Barbara CS, Stahly GP. A metastable polymorph of metformin hydrochloride: isolation and characterization using capillary crystallization and thermal microscopy techniques. *Cryst Growth Des*. 2004;4(3):441–449. Available from: <http://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/cg034243p>
10. Hariharan M, Rajan SS, Srinivasan R. *Acta Crystallogr Sect C: Cryst Struct Commun*.1989;45:911–913. Available from: <http://scripts.iucr.org/cgi-bin/paper?fe0015>
11. Bohuslavskiy Y, Voskoboinikova H, Goy A, Shishkina S. Study of the identity of the polymorphic form of API-dapagliflozin derivative and of its permanency structure under the influence of the tableting process. *Pharm Sci Pract*. 2024;(2):XX–XX. doi:10.15587/2519-4852.2024.289293.

12. Haines PJ, Wilburn FW. Thermal Analysis and Differential Scanning Calorimetry. New York: Blackie Academic and Professional; 1995. p. 63–89.
13. Yu L, Reutzel SM, Stephenson GA. *Pharm Sci Technol Today*.1998;1:118. doi:10.1016/S1461-5347(98)00031-5.
14. Boldyreva EV, Drebuschak VA, Paukov IE, Kovalevskaya YA, Drebuschak TN. *J Therm Anal Calorim*.2004;77:607. doi:10.1023/B:JTAN.0000038998.47606.27
15. Tiwari M, Chawla G, Bansal AK. Quantification of olanzapine polymorphs using powder X-ray diffraction technique. *J Pharm Sci*. [Details not provided in original reference].
16. Byrn SR, Pfeiffer RR, Stowell JG. *Solid-State Chemistry of Drugs*. 2nd ed. West Lafayette, IN: SSCI Press; 2019.
17. Ojarinta R, Kortelainen U, Laitinen R, Y liruusi J. Solid-state characterization of metformin hydrochloride and its hydrates. *Mol Pharm*. 2015;12(12):4414–4423. doi:10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.5b00546.
18. Surov AO, Solanko KA, Bond AD, Bauer-Brandl A, Karpinski PH. Polymorphism in the pharmaceutical context: theoretical considerations and experimental approaches. *Acta Crystallogr B*. 2016;72(6):954–971. doi:10.1107/S2052520616014459.
19. Harris RK. Solid-state NMR studies of pharmaceutical polymorphism. *J Pharm Sci*. 2006;95(4):859–873. doi:10.1002/jps.20593.
20. Schaefer J, Stejskal EO. Carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance of polymers spinning at the magic angle. *J Am Chem Soc*. 1976;98(4):1031–1032. doi:10.1021/ja00419a060.
21. An Q, Xing C, Wang Z, Li S, Wang W, Yang S, Kong L, Yang D, Zhang L, Du G, Lu Y. Metformin-mediated improvement in solubility, stability, and permeability of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. *Pharmaceutics*. 2024;16(3):512. doi:10.3390/pharmaceutics16030512.
22. Gupta MK, Vanarase A, Reddy P, et al. Polymorphism and its impact on the bioavailability and performance of pharmaceutical solids. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2021;12(8):4150–4159. doi:10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.12(8).4150-59.
23. Brittain HG. Polymorphism in pharmaceutical solids: an introduction. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 2017;117:3–12. doi:10.1016/j.addr.2017.06.010.
24. Thakral NK, Thakral S, Suryanarayanan R. Compression-induced polymorphic transformation in tablets: insights into mechanism and control. *J Pharm Sci*. 2019;108(2):607–619. doi:10.1016/j.xphs.2018.10.028.
25. Byrn SR, Pfeiffer RR, Stowell JG. *Solid-State Chemistry of Drugs*. 2nd ed. West Lafayette (IN): SSCI Inc.; 1999.

26. T.L. Threlfall, *Analyst*, **120**, 2435 (1995); <https://doi.org/10.1039/an9952002435>.
27. P. Láng, V. Kiss, R. Ambrus, G. Farkas, P. Szabó-Révész, Z. Aigner and E. Várkonyi, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, **84**, 177 (2013); <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2013.06.002>.
28. B.R. Jasti, J. Du and R.C. Vasavada, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 118, 161 (1995); [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5173\(94\)00325-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5173(94)00325-Y).
29. T. Uchida, E. Yonemochi, T. Oguchi, K. Terada, K. Yamamoto and Y. Nakai, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 41, 1632 (1993); <https://doi.org/10.1248/cpb.41.1632>.
30. M.M. Lowes, M.R. Caira, A.P. Lotter and J.G. Van der Watt, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 76, 744 (1987); <https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.2600760914>.
31. T.J. Cholerton, J.H. Hunt, G. Klinkert and M. Martin-Smith, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1961 (1984); <https://doi.org/10.1039/P29840001761>.
32. A. Kiss and J. Répási, *Analyst*, 118, 661 (1993); <https://doi.org/10.1039/AN9931800661>.
33. S. Botha and D. Flanagan, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 82, 195 (1992); [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5173\(92\)90175-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5173(92)90175-2).
34. H.G. Brittain, D.E. Bugay, S.J. Bogdanowich and J. Devinentis, *Drug Dev. Ind. Pharm.*, 14, 2029 (1988); <https://doi.org/10.3109/03639048809152001>.
35. K. Sasaki, H. Suzuki and H. Nakagawa, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 41, 325 (1993); <https://doi.org/10.1248/cpb.41.325>.